

Preliminary fluid inclusion data from the Amp-gabbro-norites of Ivrea town, Lower Mafic Complex, Ivrea-Verbano Zone

Stylianos Karastergios*¹, Maria L. Frezzotti¹, Rosario Esposito¹ and Simona Ferrando²

¹Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Milano-Bicocca, P.za Della Scienza 4, 20126 Milano, Italy

²Department of Earth Sciences, University of Torino, Via Valperga Caluso, 35, 1-10125 Torino, Italy

*Corresponding author's contact details (s.karastergios@campus.unimib.it)

The Ivrea Verbano Zone (IVZ) is a continental crust section located in the Southalpine domain of the Alps (NW Italy) recording late-stage Variscan metamorphism and igneous activity. The two main lithostratigraphic units in the IVZ are the metamorphic basement, called the Kinzigite Formation (KF), composed of metabasites and metapelites ranging from amphibolite to granulite-facies metamorphism and the Mafic Complex (MC), a gabbroic batholith that was emplaced at the base of the continental crust following the peak metamorphic event in the KF.

Recent studies have proven the existence of contemporaneous and immiscible melt (MI) and fluid (C-O-H) inclusions (FI) in the Grt-bearing migmatites from the KF (Carvalho et al., 2019). However, little attention has been given to the FI in the deep crustal rocks derived from the intrusion of the MC. The studied lithologies are Amp-gabbro-norites which is the most common lithology in the Lower Mafic Complex (LMC). The Amp-gabbro-norites are characterized by medium to coarse-grained granoblastic texture with triple joints, due to slow cooling in the lower crust. In this study we report the existence of carbonic multiphase inclusions (MFI) from the Amp-gabbro-norites of the LMC located in the area of Ivrea town. The FI are ubiquitous in Opx and Amp and show mainly a primary distribution (i.e., isolated large inclusions and clusters) with negative crystal shapes. The size in Opx and Amp varies from 5-10 μm , however, elongated inclusions can reach 20 μm in length and 5-7 μm in width. Opx contains biphasic FI consisting of carbonic fluid and one birefringent mineral phase. Raman microspectroscopy shows that the FI in Opx consist of pure CO_2 and Mg-Calcite (main vibration at 1088 cm^{-1}). MFI from Amp show one or two birefringent phases. Preliminary data show anatase (main vibration at 143 cm^{-1}) and dolomite (main vibration at 1095 cm^{-1}), in the absence of any fluid phase. The CO_2 density was calculated using the Raman densimeter equation of Remigi et al. (2021): $d = -0.01472000 \cdot \Delta^3 + 4.51148969 \cdot \Delta^2 - 460.27795107 \cdot \Delta + 15631.28847817$ ($R^2 = 0.994$, $SE = \pm 0.015 \text{ g/cm}^3$), where Δ , is the distance between the CO_2 upper and lower bands, as they were calculated from the Raman spectrum using a pseudo-voigt fitting. The calculated densities vary from 0.52–0.74 g/cm^3 ; these values are probably underestimated due to the presence of Mg-calcite in the FI. Further investigation in the other minerals of the assemblage (e.g., Pl and Cpx) will provide an integrated view of the composition of the fluids and solids included in the Amp-gabbro-norites.

References:

- Carvalho, B. B., et al. (2019). Anatexis and fluid regime of the deep continental crust: New clues from melt and fluid inclusions in metapelitic migmatites from Ivrea Zone (NW Italy). *J Metamorph Geol*, 37(7), 951–975. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmg.12463>
- Remigi, S. et al. (2021). Interlaboratory Application of Raman CO_2 Densimeter Equations: Experimental Procedure and Statistical Analysis Using Bootstrapped Confidence Intervals. *Applied Spectroscopy*, 75(7), 867–881. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0003702820987601>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956127